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Research Article

Comparative Study on Formulated Topical Cream Containing Butterfly Pea Flower and Hibiscus

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ABSTRACT

Current study aimed to the comparative study on formulated topical cream containing butterfly pea flower and hibiscus for anti-aging property. Creams are semi-solid emulsions which contain mixtures of oil and water. For cosmetic purposes, pharmaceutical creams have a variety of applications such as cleansing, beautifying, altering appearance, moisturizing etc. Creams are also used to protect skin against bacterial, fungal infections as well as healing cuts, burns, wounds on the skin. People's perception towards traditional medicine has also changed and is very encouraging. In this study, cream were formulated based on antiaging property of cream and its evaluation. Butterfly pea flower or Clitoria ternatea L. is a member of family Fabaceae. It is rich in antioxidants and used in reducing redness, soothes skin irritation, reduces inflammations. Hibiscus or Hibiscus rosa sinensis is a member of family Malvaceae. It is used as anti-inflammatory, moisturizer, exfoliator, skin brightening, skin whitening. Butterfly pea flower and hibiscus containing anthocyanin which are natural antioxidants that slows down the aging process. By formulating a cream with Butterfly pea flower extract and hibiscus extract, we aimed to develop topical creams that slows down aging process which gives an antiaging effect.

INTRODUCTION

Cream is defined as semisolid emulsions which are oil in water (o/w) or water in oil (w/o) type and these semisolid emulsions are intended for external application. Cream is classified as oil in water and water in oil emulsion. It is applied on outer part or superficial part of the skin and its main ability is to remain for a longer period of time

at the site of application. The function of a skin cream is to protect the skin against different environmental condition, weather and soothing effect to the skin. The main aim of our work is to develop a herbal cream containing butterfly pea flower and hibiscus which can give anti-aging property which reduce wrinkles, dry skin and rashes, reduce acne and skin irritation, moisturizer,

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sunscreen, and also adding glow to the skin. The four herbal ingredients can be used in the formulation which are butterfly pea flower, hibiscus, aloe vera and neem. The butterfly pea or *Clitoria ternatea* L. is a member of Fabaceae family. Butterfly pea flower is rich in antioxidants and used in reducing redness, soothes skin irritation, reduces inflammation. Hibiscus or *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* is a member of Malvaceae. Hibiscus is used as anti-inflammatory, moisturizer, exfoliator, skin brightening, skin whitening. Aloe vera gel is used as a moisturizer to reduce pimples and acne and also used for treatment of burns, wounds. Neem is used as an antifungal and anti-inflammatory and it is also used to reduce scar, pigmentation and itching of the skin. The blue colour of the butterfly pea flower and red colour of hibiscus indicates the presence of anthocyanins which is responsible for its anti-aging effect.[9]

Aim And Objectives

The aim of the present work is to formulate a topical cream enriched with butterfly pea flower and hibiscus extracts for its anti-aging property and comparison of the formulated topical cream.

The objective of present study includes: to extract constituent of butterfly pea flower and hibiscus, to extract aloe vera gel and neem oil, to formulate anti-aging cream using extract of butterfly pea flower and hibiscus and to evaluate and compare the formulated preparation

Review Of Literature

1. **P.K. Sudhakar., et al., (2020)** investigated to provide an overview of the medicinal properties and traditional uses of *Clitoria ternatea* (commonly known as butterfly pea). They focus on the plant's therapeutic potential

and its role in various traditional medicine systems

2. **Bala, R., et al., (2022)** evaluated phytochemical and pharmacological parameters of Hibiscus Rosa Sinensis Lin.: This review aims to present recent details on botany, ethnomedicinal uses, photochemistry, pharmacological effects, toxic effects with the purpose to find research gaps demanding for upcoming research and investigation of Hibiscus Rosa Sinensis Linn.
3. **Pradip D. Dhangar., et al., (2023)** investigated the formulation and evaluation of herbal extract of Butterfly Pea Multipurpose Cream. This review aims to develop a herbal cream which can give multipurpose effect, like moisturizer, reduce acne and skin irritation, reduce skin problems like eczema, psoriasis, dry skin, wrinkles, rashes etc. and also adding glow to the face.
4. **S.K. Sharma., et al., (2023)** evaluated pharmacological properties of *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*, commonly known as hibiscus. The paper discusses the various bioactive compounds in hibiscus and their potential therapeutic effects.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Ingredients: Butterfly pea flower extract, hibiscus flower extract, neem extract, aloe vera extract, beeswax, borax, methylparaben, liquid paraffin, rose water, distilled water

Collection: Neem *Azadirachta indica* and aloe vera *Aloe barberensis* were collected from local areas of Mundakkayam and Butterfly pea flower *Clitoria ternatea* and Hibiscus *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* were collected from local areas of Chenappady.

Fig.No.1: Dried Butterfly pea flower

Fig.No.2: Dried hibiscus flower

Equipment: The equipment used are mechanical stirrer, digital pH meter, electronic balance

Extraction: The extraction were carried out using Soxhlet apparatus. The butterfly pea flower and hibiscus placed in a thimble-shaped filter paper which is then kept in a glass cylinder. This cylinder is provided with a siphon tube and an inlet tube. A water condenser is attached to the cylinder at the top. This entire assembly is fitted into the neck of a round bottom flask containing the water. The flask is heated in a water bath or sand bath. The solvent vapours reach the cylinder through the inlet tube and conduce on passing upward into the condenser. The condensed solvent comes in contact with the crude organic substance and dissolves it. As soon as the solution reaches the top end of the siphon tube. In this way, a continuous supply of solvent vapours is maintained in the cylinder, and the dissolved organic compound flows back into the flask. Finally, the heating is stopped and the solution in the flask is distilled to recover the solvent, while the organic compound is left behind. It takes almost 1-2hrs to complete the extraction process. Neem and aloe vera were extracted using reflux condenser which is attached to the cylinder at the top. This is fitted into the neck of a round bottom flask containing the water. The flask is heated in a water bath or sand bath. The solvent vapours reach the cylinder through the

inlet tube and conduce on passing upward into the condenser. The condensed solvent comes in contact with the crude organic substance and dissolves it. As soon as the solution reaches the top end of the siphon tube. In this way, a continuous supply of solvent vapours is maintained in the cylinder, and the dissolved organic compound flows back into the flask. Finally, the heating is stopped and the solution in the flask is distilled to recover the solvent, while the organic compound is left behind. It takes almost 30-60 minutes to complete the extraction process

Formulation of butterfly pea flower and hibiscus extract cream

Heat liquid paraffin and beeswax in a borosilicate glass beaker at 75°C and maintain that heating temperature (oil phase). In another beaker, dissolve borax, methyl paraben in distilled water and heat. This is also heated to 75°C to dissolve borax and methyl paraben and to get a clear solution (aqueous phase). Then add a measured amount of aloe vera gel, neem extract, butterfly pea flower extract and hibiscus extract. Stir vigorously until it forms a smooth cream. Then add few drops of rose oil and a fragrance. Put this cream on the slab and add few drops of distilled water, if necessary and mix the cream in a geometrical manner on.[4][6][7]

Fig. No.3: Formulation of Hibiscus cream

Fig.No.4: Formulation of hibiscus cream

Table No.1: Composition of butterfly pea and hibiscus extract cream

Ingredients	F1	F2
Butterfly pea flower extract	3ml	-
Hibiscus extract	-	3ml
Beeswax	6g	6g
Liquid paraffin	20ml	20ml
Borax	0.4g	0.4g

Methyl paraben	0.04g	0.04g
Rose water	1 or 2 drops	1 or 2 drops
Aloe vera gel	1ml	1ml
Neem oil	1ml	1ml
Water	12ml	12ml

Fig.No.5: Extraction of hibiscus cream

Fig.No.6: Extraction of hibiscus

Fig.No.7: Butterfly pea flower extract

Fig. No.8: Hibiscus extract

Fig. No. 9: Neem extract

Fig. No. 10: Aloe vera extract

RESULTS

1. Physical appearance

Table No.2: Physical appearance

Formulation	Color	Odour	State	Consistency
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Butterfly pea flower	Light purple	Pleasant	Semi solid	Smooth
Hibiscus	Light pink	Pleasant	Semi solid	Smooth

Fig. No.11: Butterfly cream flower

Fig. No.12: Hibiscus cream

2. pH of the cream:

The pH of the formulated cream is determined to ensure its compatibility with the skin's natural pH, which typically ranges from 4.5 to 6.5. A compatible pH helps maintain the skin's barrier

function, prevents irritation and supports overall skin health.[6][9]

Table No.3: pH of formulated cream

Formulation	pH
Butterfly pea flower	5.55
Hibiscus	4.54

Fig. No.13: Ph meter showing viscosity of Butterfly pea flower cream

Fig. No.14: Ph meter showing hibiscus cream

3. Homogeneity:

The developed cream was tested for homogeneity by visual inspection for appearance and presence of any lumps, flocculates or aggregates. The homogeneity was found to be good for all formulations.

4. Spreadability:

The Spreadability of the cream is carried out by using 0.25g of semi-solid product which is placed between two glass slides. A standardized weight of 10g is applied on the top of the slide for 5 min, after which the spread diameter of the product is measured to assess its Spreadability

Table No.4: Spreadability

Formulation	Time	Spreadability
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Butterfly pea flower	5min	32
Hibiscus	5min	42

Fig.No.15: Spreadability

5.Phase separation:

Table No.5: Phase separation

Formulation	Phase separation
Butterfly pea flower	No phase separation
Hibiscus	No phase separation

The viscosity of cream is measured using Brookfield viscometer.

Table No.6: Viscosity

Formulation	Viscosity
Butterfly pea flower	34349 mPa
Hibiscus	18369 mPa

6.Viscosity

Fig.No.16: Brookfield viscometer showing viscosity of butterfly pea flower cream

Fig.No.17: Brookfield viscometer showing viscosity of hibiscus cream

7. Dye solubility test:

The amaranth dye is mixed with cream. Place one drop of cream on a microscopic slide cover it with a cover slip and examine it under a microscope. The dispersed globules appear in red color and ground is colorless. Hence the formulation was found to be W/O emulsion.

Fig. No.18: Dye solubility

Color	Light purple	Light purple
pH	5.55	5.55
Homogeneity	Good	Good

For Hibiscus

Parameter	Initial days	First month
Color	Light pink	Light pink
pH	4.54	4.54
Homogeneity	Good	Good

Table No.7: Stability studies data for optimized formulation For Butterfly pea flower

Parameter	Initial days	First month
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7.2 Phytochemical screening

7.2.1 Phytochemical screening of Butterfly pea flower extract

Table No.8: Phytochemical screening of Butterfly pea flower extract

Phytoconstituent	Observation	Inference
a) Anthocyanin	Purple to pink red to blue color was produced.	<p>Fig.No.19 Confirms the presence of anthocyanin.</p>
b) Alkaloids	Orange precipitate was produced.	<p>Fig.No.20 Indicate the presence of alkaloids</p>
c) Glycoside	Red color was obtained	<p>Fig.No.21 Indicate the presence of glycosides</p>

d) Flavonoids	yellow color was produced.	<p>Fig.No.22 Indicate the presence of flavonoids</p>
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Table No.9: Phytochemical screening of hibiscus extract

Phytoconstituent	Observation	Inference
a) Anthocyanin	Red to blue color was produced	<p>Fig.No.23 Confirms the presence of anthocyanin.</p>
b) Alkaloids	Orange color precipitate produced.	<p>Fig.No.24 Indicate the presence of alkaloids</p>
c) Glycosides	Red color was obtained	<p>Fig.No.25 Indicate the presence of glycosides.</p>
d) Flavonoids	Greenish yellow color was produced.	

Quantitative analysis

For Butterfly pea flower

$$C = \frac{A}{\epsilon \times l}$$

Absorbance of butterfly pea flower(A)=3.330

Molar absorptivity(ϵ) of anthocyanin = 34,300 L⁻¹mol⁻¹cm⁻¹

Path length(l)= 1cm

Concentration= 0.000097084

Concentration in microgram=concentration \times molecular weight of anthocyanin

Concentration =

0.000097084 \times 449.2=0.0436 μ g/ml

For Hibiscus

$$C = \frac{A}{\epsilon \times l}$$

Absorbance of Hibiscus(A)=1.580

Molar absorptivity(ϵ) of anthocyanin = 34,300 L⁻¹mol⁻¹cm⁻¹

Path length(l)= 1cm

Concentration=0.00004606

Concentration in microgram=concentration \times molecular weight of anthocyanin

Concentration= 0.00004606 \times 449.2 = 0.020690 μ g/ml

DISCUSSION

The present work was the comparison between two formulated topical cream, one is with butterfly

pea flower and other is with hibiscus flower. Both the creams are water in oil (W/O) type emulsion. The physical appearance of butterfly pea flower was light purple and that of hibiscus was light pink. Both the creams were tested for homogeneity by visual inspection for appearance and presence of any lumps, flocculates or aggregates. The pH of butterfly pea flower cream was 5.55 and that of hibiscus was 4.54. The viscosity of butterfly pea flower was 34349mPa and that of hibiscus was 18369 mPa. Spreadability of butterfly pea flower was 32 and that of hibiscus was 42. There was no phase separation observed during the study of both the cream. Anthocyanin is the constituent which is responsible for the antiaging effect of both the extract of butterfly pea flower and hibiscus. The concentration of anthocyanin is more in butterfly pea flower than hibiscus. So, on comparing both the cream butterfly pea flower cream has more antiaging property than hibiscus.

CONCLUSION

The objective of our project is to compare the antiaging property of two creams, one with butterfly pea flower and other with hibiscus. Initially, the research work started with a wide and thorough literature survey. Butterfly pea flower and hibiscus were collected and dried using hot air oven. Butterfly pea flower extract, hibiscus extract, beeswax, borax, liquid paraffin, methyl paraben, neem, aloe vera gel, rose water were used in the formulation. Anthocyanin is the constituent is responsible for the antiaging effect of both the extract of butterfly pea flower and hibiscus.

Phytochemical screening were carried out for both the extracts. Evaluations of the creams were carried out. The organoleptic evaluation of the cream was done. In this, the creams were observed for color, odour, texture, state, and homogeneity. The color of butterfly pea flower cream was light purple and that of hibiscus cream was light pink. Both the creams were found to be in semisolid state and are homogenic in nature. The flowers were extracted using Soxhlet apparatus with water as solvent. The phytochemical screening was done for both the creams to identify the presence of anthocyanin, alkaloids, glycosides and flavonoids. Quantitative analysis of both the extract were carried out to determine the concentration of anthocyanin which is responsible for antiaging effect. For identifying the type of emulsion, a dye solubility test was carried out by using amaranth dye. The dispersed globules appeared red in color and ground colorless. Thus, it confirms the formulated cold cream is a W/O type of emulsion. pH of cream containing butterfly pea flower was 5.55 and that of hibiscus was 4.54 respectively. Spreadability test were carried out for both the creams and the cream containing butterfly pea flower shows better spreadability. The spreadability was expressed in terms of time in seconds taken by two slides to slip off from the cream, placed in between the slides, under a certain load. Lesser the time taken for the separation of the two slides, better the spreadability. Viscosity of both the cream were carried out using Brookfield viscometer and butterfly pea flower cream shows better viscosity. The phase separation of both the creams were carried out. Both the cream formulations exhibit good stability with no significant phase separation observed under the tested condition. The stability of both the cream was found to be stable during the initial days and the cream is kept undisturbed for one month.

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